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Climate Risk STAC: A living metadata catalog of geospatial data for climate risk assessments

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ABSTRACT

Climate risks are increasing globally due to climate change, driven by intensifying climate hazards and changes in socioeconomic conditions that drive exposure and vulnerability. Climate Risk Assessments (CRAs) constitute a tool to understand such risks based on the analysis of geospatial datasets. However, CRA data are often scattered across different platforms, thereby inhibiting their Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR). To make CRA data FAIR, we develop Climate Risk STAC, a living metadata catalog of open-access geospatial datasets that is hosted in a collaborative environment for continuous development. Climate Risk STAC (version 1.0) currently includes 214 metadata entries from nine different hazards, five types of exposed elements, and seven vulnerability categories. All data entries can be explored in a user-friendly browser which eases data selection. We encourage contributions of new datasets to maintain a growing, community-led catalog that reflects state-of-the-art CRA concepts and data.

1. Introduction

Globally, population and assets such as buildings and infrastructure are increasingly at risk from natural hazards including storms, extreme heat, floods (e.g. pluvial, fluvial, coastal) and wildfires, which are expected to increase in frequency and intensity due to climate change (IPCC, 2022). The impacts of such climate hazards are further driven by evolving socioeconomic conditions that determine the exposure and vulnerability of assets and people in at-risk locations (Dodman et al., 2022; Field, 2012; Thiery et al., 2021). For instance, population growth and urbanization processes may lead to human displacements, increasing mortality rates, and asset damage (EM-DAT, 2021; Mester et al., 2023). Climate Risk Assessments (CRAs) are a tool to examine such risks under current as well as future conditions by analyzing geospatial data, and constitute an important building block for the development of adaptation strategies (Simpson et al., 2021). CRAs can help

establish risk hotspots at the global scale and thereby provide the basis for the prioritization of adaptation as formulated by the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2015), the UN's 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations, 2015), and the Paris Agreement on climate change (UNFCCC, 2016).

The majority of current CRAs employ the conceptual risk framework of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) where risk results from the interaction of three risk drivers[†]: climate hazards, exposure to these hazards, and vulnerability of the exposed elements (Ara Begum et al., 2022; Field, 2012; Oppenheimer et al., 2014). Within this overarching framework, various methods for conducting risk assessments are available in the literature. One commonly employed method at the global scale involves assessing the exposure of populations (e.g. Chambers, 2020; Dullaart et al., 2021; Mora et al., 2017; Neumann et al., 2015; Tuholske et al., 2021) and/or assets (e.g. Hinkel et al., 2014; Jongman et al., 2012; Marzeion and Levermann, 2014).

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[†] The latest IPCC Assessment Report (AR6) has put forward an updated risk framework that includes the fourth risk determinant 'response' (Ara Begum et al., 2022; Simpson et al., 2021), which has not yet been accounted for in global CRAs. This living catalog therefore focusses on hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, but can easily be extended when data of the fourth risk determinant are available.

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Other methods include index-based approaches that normalize the product of hazard, exposure and vulnerability to represent risk intensity (e.g. Carrão et al., 2016; Meza et al., 2020) and probabilistic approaches based on hazard return intervals, exposed assets, and vulnerability expressed by damage functions depending on hazard intensity (e.g. Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019; Jongman et al., 2015; Koks et al., 2019; Koks and Haer, 2020; Kropf et al., 2022; Tiggeloven et al., 2020; Voudoukas et al., 2020; Winsemius et al., 2016).

Assessing risk from climate hazards in a consistent manner includes selection and processing of suitable geospatial datasets on hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. This can be a daunting task as relevant datasets are scattered across different data platforms and portals (Wilkinson et al., 2016). In particular, climate (i.e. hazard) and socio-economic (i.e. exposure and vulnerability) data are usually available through distinct data platforms such as the Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) (Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), 2025), the Planetary Computer Data Catalog (Microsoft, 2025), and the European Commission Joint Research Centre's Data Catalogue (European Commission Joint Research Centre, 2025) for hazard data; and the Global Data Lab (GDL) (Global Data Lab, 2026) for exposure and vulnerability data. Furthermore, data on risk drivers are often produced as part of research projects but are usually made available through a variety of repositories such as Zenodo, Figshare, and Dataverse. These general data repositories cater for a wide range of disciplines and therefore do not focus on presenting data in a structured manner (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

The continuous increase in global data relevant for CRAs presents a challenge for potential users to stay up to date regarding the latest datasets. Furthermore, there is currently a lack of guidance on how to select, process, and harmonize CRA data, such that the data are easy to access and analyze for potential users (Fakhrudin et al., 2022). To address challenges like these, the FAIR data principles have been developed in recent years to ease the reuse of data in research, facilitating the provision of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data, with particular emphasis on machine-readability and -accessibility (Wilkinson et al., 2016). The FAIR principles have become the new standard in data provisioning and research (e.g. Iturbide et al., 2022; Kerfant et al., 2023; Rocca-Serra et al., 2023; Scheffler et al., 2022; Welter et al., 2023).

Several collaborative efforts have initiated catalogs and syntheses of open-access datasets relevant for CRAs in recent years, thereby contributing to making data FAIR. Examples are the POPGRID Data Collaborative (POPGRID, 2020) that offers comparison of exposure datasets (i.e. population, urban extents) to facilitate their use in specific applications (Leyk et al., 2019); Resource Watch which offers an inventory of over 350 geospatial datasets at global scale, broadly related to the world's resources and citizens around 12 broad topics (e.g. energy, climate, forests, coral reefs); Oasis HUB that currently lists over 1,000 catastrophe, extreme weather and environmental risk datasets at varying spatial scales; the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction's (UNDRR) Risk Information Exchange (RiX) that catalogs data on the three risk drivers at national to global scales, also including a selection of geospatial datasets; as well as the work of Lindersson et al. (2020) who

assembled an overview of global data for assessing floods, droughts, and their interaction with humans.

While these data inventories contain geospatial datasets applicable to CRAs, they have two main limitations (Table 1): a) because they do not specifically focus on CRAs, some datasets may be irrelevant, requiring users to rely on their own expert judgment to select appropriate datasets; and b) they offer limited opportunities to contribute new datasets, therefore running into the risk of becoming outdated. To address these challenges, we develop Climate Risk STAC, a living metadata catalog of geospatial CRA data that adheres to the FAIR data principles. This catalog provides:

- a) an inventory of open-access geospatial datasets along the three main risk drivers hazard, exposure and vulnerability that can readily be used as input into CRAs;
- b) a flexible, customizable, and collaborative environment with the opportunity to contribute further datasets with the help of a data submission form.

We envision creating a living catalog of publicly available geospatial datasets relevant for CRAs along all drivers of climate risks, with detailed metadata attributes such as their spatial and temporal resolution, underlying modeling approach and code available for processing the data. Therefore, the catalog is attractive for different users (e.g. risk experts, researchers, data analysts) to browse and select CRA datasets. Inspired by other community-driven catalogs (Montero et al., 2023; Stern et al., 2022), another important feature of Climate Risk STAC is that it is continuously updated by the CRA community. In this article, we present the first version of Climate Risk STAC with its focus on global-scale CRA data and showcase how it can be used and expanded by the CRA community, thereby streamlining CRA data discovery while applying the FAIR data principles.

2. Methods

In this section we introduce the catalog structure along the three risk drivers; the criteria used for data selection; and the metadata attributes recorded per dataset. Furthermore, we describe the technical implementation according to the SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) specification as well as the opportunity to contribute additional datasets via the collaborative and version control platform GitHub. A schematic overview of the study design is presented in Fig. 1.

2.1. Catalog structure

As the aim of Climate Risk STAC is to assemble datasets useful for CRAs, we structure the catalog along the three risk drivers based on the IPCC risk framework (Ara Begum et al., 2022; Field, 2012; Oppenheimer et al., 2014). The first level of the catalog classification scheme (Fig. 2) distinguishes a) hazard (i.e. climate) data versus b) exposure and vulnerability (i.e. socioeconomic) data. The second level of the classification scheme groups the data into six hazard and four exposure and

Table 1

Examples of initiatives that provide inventories of open-access geospatial datasets potentially relevant for CRAs with their pros and cons.

Initiative name	Spatial scale	Pros	Cons	Reference
POPGRID Data Collaborative	Global	Global scale, focus on geospatial data	Exposure only	Leyk et al. (2019); POPGRID (2020)
Resource Watch	Global	Global scale, focus on geospatial data	Lacking focus on CRAs	World Resources Institute (2025)
Oasis HUB	Varying	Large number and variety of datasets	Hazard only	OasisHUB (2025)
UNDRR Risk Information Exchange (RiX)	National to global	Focus on risk assessments, all risk drivers included	Lacking focus on climate hazards or geospatial data, broad range of datasets limits usability for CRA community	UNDRR (2025)
Lindersson et al.	Global	Global scale, all risk drivers included	Limited to droughts and floods, static	Lindersson et al. (2020)

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the study design. Summary of each step taken in assembling the living metadata catalog.

Fig. 2. Classification scheme underlying the catalog structure. The catalog distinguishes a) hazard data and b) exposure and vulnerability data. The data are split into six and four categories, respectively (grey boxes). Hazard data are further classified into 11, exposure data into five, and vulnerability data into eight subcategories (colored boxes).

vulnerability categories (grey boxes), which are further classified into 11, five, and eight subcategories, respectively (colored boxes). This structure is harmonized with current standards for data provisioning and reporting as follows:

a) Hazard: We split climate hazards into six categories based on so-called Hazard Information Profiles (HIPs) (Murray et al., 2021) developed by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) to support the implementation of the Sendai Framework,

the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Paris Agreement (UNDRR-ISC, 2020). The majority of climate hazards in this first version of Climate Risk STAC belongs to the meteorological and hydrological hazard profile, including floods, precipitation related, temperature related, and wind related hazards, while wildfires belong to the environmental hazard profile. We extend this list with a category for datasets that characterize the co-occurrence of multiple hazards, thereby accommodating the growing need for multi-hazard CRAs (Ward et al., 2022). We align these hazard profiles with hazard types from the Risk Data Library Standard (RDLS), which has recently been established by the Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery (GFDRR) and provides an open metadata standard specifically designed for datasets relevant for risk assessments (Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery, 2023). This process results in a CRA-specific classification scheme as presented in Fig. 2a.

b) **Exposure and vulnerability:** We distinguish four categories of exposed elements: population, buildings, infrastructure, and land use (Fig. 2b). This classification is based on the exposure categories defined in the RDLS and is harmonized with the UNDRR Risk Information Exchange (RiX) (UNDRR, 2025). As the relevant vulnerability characteristics are directly related to the exposed elements, we group the vulnerability data according to the four exposure categories as well. While the classification of the vulnerability data is loosely based on the RDLS and UNDRR RiX, common classification standards for these data are scarce as current global CRAs rarely assess vulnerability in a spatially explicit manner. Therefore, the categories presented here can easily be extended with additional categories when new data become available.

2.2. Data selection

To ensure that we include datasets relevant for CRAs, we define a set of basic selection criteria. First, we focus on geospatial datasets that can be either in raster format, vector data (i.e. points, polygons, polylines) at a subnational level (i.e. administrative units), or tabular data that include coordinates. Furthermore, we include observed and modeled datasets that can reflect historical conditions as well as future projections under climatic and socioeconomic scenarios. To meet the FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), the data need to be published under an open-access license with a persistent identifier assigned to it (e.g. a Digital Object Identifier, DOI). While we focus on datasets published in peer-reviewed journals, we also include other data if documentation of the methods used for data collection, aggregation, and processing is available via the data provider's website.

To keep the number of included datasets manageable for this first version of the catalog, we assemble global-scale data only. Later versions of Climate Risk STAC can include data at different spatial scales, which can easily be integrated into the current catalog structure (see section 2.5). Furthermore, we focus on datasets that are readily available to be used as input into a CRA, i.e. representing spatial footprints of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. For instance, for coastal flood hazards, we include maps of coastal flood extents or depths rather than data on the components that drive coastal flooding such as storm surge height, wave height, or tides. For hazards where hazard footprint maps are not readily available, we include climate variables that can be used to derive those footprints (e.g. monthly statistics of daily minimum temperature for deriving cold waves). Essentially, we strive to provide at least one relevant dataset per subcategory classified in Fig. 2 (i.e. colored boxes).

The actual data selection process has been a joint effort as part of the author team as well as collaborators of the CLIMAAX project which pursues the aim to develop a customized framework and toolbox for CRAs across Europe (The CLIMAAX community, 2025). Experts working on at least one of the three risk drivers provided the metadata attributes (see section 2.3) of those geospatial datasets that they were familiar with. If datasets of a specific subcategory were missing, the team

reached out to additional experts on the subcategory in question. In total, 15 experts contributed to the data entries in this first version of Climate Risk STAC. As a living resource, it is not exhaustive and depends on continued data contributions from the CRA community.

2.3. Metadata attributes

For each dataset included in Climate Risk STAC, we define 34 metadata attributes that provide relevant information for CRAs. These attributes are derived from the RDLS (Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery, 2023), harmonized with the requirements of STAC (Radiant Earth Foundation, 2021) (see section 2.4), and extended with further attributes relevant for CRAs. Such custom extensions include links to publicly available resources such as publications and code (e.g. for data processing or download), underlying data sources, and notes for using the data. Table 2 lists a selected set (27) of the attributes included in the catalog along with their names, which we have adopted from the RDLS or STAC if available. It further provides a brief attribute description and marks the attributes available in the RDLS, STAC, and our custom extensions. Selected attributes are additionally used as keywords in the browsable catalog (attribute name marked with “**”). Supplementary Table 1 provides a complete list of all metadata attributes.

2.4. Technical implementation

We use the STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog) specification (Radiant Earth Foundation, 2021) for the technical implementation of the living catalog. STAC provides a common standard for structuring and querying geospatial metadata (Emanuele, 2020) and therefore provides a foundation for making data FAIR. A STAC catalog consists of JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) files, with the STAC Item at its center, which is a GeoJSON feature encoding the item's geographic coverage and temporal extent. These (Geo)JSON files follow a number of core specifications but can be extended flexibly to accommodate additional metadata attributes (Radiant Earth Foundation, 2021). Therefore, STAC provides a suitable basis for implementing the variety of attributes relevant for CRAs as defined in Table 2 and Supplementary Table 1. A STAC catalog contains metadata only, with each data entry linking to the platform that hosts the underlying data. This lightweight structure allows STAC to support thousands of data entries without substantial storage needs (Radiant Earth Foundation, 2021).

The process of building Climate Risk STAC is automated with the help of PySTAC (stac-utils, 2026), a library for working with STAC in Python 3, which allows for reading, writing, creating and manipulating STAC catalogs. The three main steps for compiling the living catalog can be summarized as follows (see GitHub for the full workflow (Reimann et al., 2026)):

1. **Catalogs:** The metadata attributes *Catalog* and *Category* are used to build the STAC catalogs, which constitute the underlying folder structure of the living catalog.
2. **Collections** are created and added to their respective catalog folder. They include data entries from the same general data source, specifying the overall spatial extent and temporal coverage, the license, provider(s), and keywords.
3. **Items:** Individual data entries are created and added to their respective collection. Items provide all metadata attributes specific to the individual data entry, including technical specifications (e.g. data type and format, coordinate reference system, spatial resolution), and broader attributes such as subcategory, spatial scale, reference period or publication link and type. Each item has at least one **asset** associated with it, which links to a download page or direct data download.

The resulting catalog is transformed into a browsable HTML page,

Table 2
Selected metadata attributes and descriptions underlying the living catalog. Attributes available in RDLs, STAC and custom extensions are marked with “x”. Attributes used as keywords in the browsable catalog are marked with “*”. A complete list of all metadata attributes is available in [Supplementary Table 1](#).

Attribute name	Description	RDLs	STAC	Custom
Catalog	Overarching catalog that the data belong to (i.e. hazard, exposure-vulnerability; Fig. 2)	x	x	
Category	Category of data type according to classification scheme (Fig. 2 , grey boxes)	x	x	
Subcategory*	Subcategory of data type according to classification scheme (Fig. 2 , colored boxes)	x		
Risk data type*	Risk driver (i.e. hazard, exposure, vulnerability)	x		
Collection title	Name of the dataset collection; the collection title must be the same for each item belonging to that collection		x	
Collection description	Detailed description of the dataset collection; the collection description must be the same for each item belonging to that collection		x	
Item title	Concise name of the dataset item; each item from the same collection needs to have a unique name		x	
Item description	Detailed description of the dataset item; if there is only one item in the collection, the collection description can be used		x	
Spatial scale*	Spatial coverage of the dataset (i.e. (near-)global, regional, national, subnational)	x		
Bbox	Bounding box (i.e. spatial extent) of the dataset given in WGS84 coordinates (xmin, ymin, xmax, ymax)	x	x	
Reference period*	Reference period for which the data are available (i.e. historical, future, historical & future)			x
Temporal coverage	Temporal coverage of the data in years (i.e. YYYY for one time step; YYYY-YYYY for time series; YYYY-now if data are updated in real time)	x	x	
Data type	Geospatial data type (i.e. raster, vector, tabular)			x
Data format	Geospatial data format (e.g. geotiff, geopackage, shapefile, geodatabase, csv)	x	x	
Spatial resolution	Spatial resolution in numeric value; or as a string (e.g. “administrative unit”, “feature level”, “event”)	x		
Coordinate reference system	Numerical code (e.g. EPSG, ESRI code) of the coordinate reference system (CRS) (e.g. 4326, 54009)	x	x	
Source type*	Indicates whether the data is directly observed from real-world measurements or generated through modeling or simulations (i.e. observed, modeled)	x		
Underlying data	(optional) data underlying the analysis type (see Supplementary Table 1)			x
Provider name	Name of data provider	x	x	
Provider role	Role of data provider (i.e. licensor, producer, processor, host)	x	x	
License	Data distribution license (e.g. CCO-1.0, CC-BY-4.0, CC-BY-SA-4.0)	x	x	

Table 2 (continued)

Attribute name	Description	RDLs	STAC	Custom
Data overview link	URL to website where the dataset is described and can be accessed	x		
Publication link	(optional) link to publication (DOI if possible)	x	x	
Publication type	(optional) type of publication (e.g. report, article, documentation)			x
Code link*	(optional) link to available code (DOI if possible)			x
Code type	(optional) type of available code (e.g. data download, processing, application)			x
Asset links	URL to specific data files (if available), otherwise same as Data overview link (separated with a space: ' ')	x	x	

using STAC Browser ([Radiant Earth Foundation, 2025](#)). This way, all data entries in Climate Risk STAC can be browsed by risk driver (i.e. hazard, exposure-vulnerability) and category (e.g. flood, wind-related; buildings, population), and can be filtered by title, description, and keywords. Furthermore, the browser supports labeling of e.g. keywords and data formats, and it provides direct links to specific attributes such as the data license, available code, and data download. As STAC Browser allows for exploring the living catalog in a user-friendly manner, a wide range of users with different levels of expertise (e.g. risk experts, researchers, data analysts) will be able to use it when searching for CRA datasets.

2.5. Contribution of new datasets

New datasets can be contributed via GitHub (free user account needed) where we provide two data submission forms, one for hazard data and one for exposure and vulnerability data, with additional guidance on how to fill in the form ([Reimann et al., 2026](#)). In the submission forms, we provide brief definitions per metadata attribute along with example entries and make use of pre-defined drop-down menus and required field entries. This way, we ease the contribution of new data entries and ensure that the suggested entries meet the technical requirements of STAC.

Once a new dataset has been suggested via the submission form, it is validated to ensure the technical quality and reliability of the newly added data entry. After an initial screening for potential duplicates, we verify that all metadata entries meet the technical requirements of STAC. Although the submission form includes drop-down menus and required fields, free-text entries can still introduce errors (e.g., entering characters instead of numbers), which may cause the catalog build to fail. Once the technical quality of a submission is confirmed, we assess the reliability of the underlying data by checking for an open-access license with a persistent identifier and the availability of technical documentation on the data provider's website. If all checks are successful, the dataset is accepted and the catalog is rebuilt automatically; otherwise, the data contributor is asked to revise their submission. At present, this entire process is fully moderated by the repository administrators.

The provided data submission forms are designed such that they allow for new data contributions beyond the categories and spatial scale established in this first version of Climate Risk STAC. Thus, datasets on the fourth risk determinant (i.e. response), additional subcategories (e.g. snowstorm/blizzard; adaptive capacity), and further spatial scales (i.e. regional, national, subnational) can be added, thereby facilitating a continuously growing, community-led catalog that reflects the current state-of-the-art in CRA concepts and data.

3. Results: Climate Risk STAC

The latest release of Climate Risk STAC is available in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18628912>) (Reimann et al., 2026), linking directly to the GitHub (Reimann et al., 2026) repository. The catalog documentation is directly accessible via <https://climate-risk-data.github.io/climate-risk-stac/> (Reimann et al., 2026).

3.1. Catalog inventory

The presented version (v1.0) of Climate Risk STAC includes 214 data entries (items) that belong to 84 distinct datasets (collections). Hazard data constitute roughly 43% of the data entries, followed by 37% for exposure data and 20% for vulnerability data (Fig. 3). Of all hazard data entries (n = 92), the temperature-related hazards heat waves (18) and cold waves (8) make up the largest share and form, together with floods that include fluvial (16), coastal (3) and not specified (6) floods, more than half of the hazard data entries. Precipitation-related hazards make up another quarter of the data entries, while environmental (i.e. wild-fires), wind-related hazards (i.e. tropical (6) and extratropical cyclones (2)) and multi-hazard (1) constitute about 20% of all hazard entries. More than half of the exposure data entries (n = 79) fall into the land use category, which includes urban/built-up land (25) and land use/land cover (17) datasets. Another third of the data entries are population data (25), and roughly 15% are data entries of infrastructure (8) and buildings (4). Over 60% of the vulnerability data (n = 43) are population-related characteristics that comprise demographics (12), socioeconomic status (12), and composite vulnerability indices (2). Land use characteristics (i.e. urban/built-up land (5) and land use/land cover (2)), infrastructure characteristics (5) and building characteristics (5) make up the remaining ~40%.

Regarding the technical specifications of all data entries, roughly 80% are available in raster format, while tabular and vector data make up roughly 10% each. The spatial resolution of the data ranges from 10

m to 2 decimal degrees (~222 km at the equator) for raster or tabular data, and from individual stations or features to different administrative unit levels for vector data. Furthermore, almost three quarters of the recorded data are available for historical periods, reaching as far back as 10,000 BC; about 17% of the data entries are future projections, up to the year 2100 for exposure and vulnerability and 2300 for hazard data; the remaining data entries (9%) provide both historical data and future projections. Moreover, 94% of the data entries are linked to a publication, with about half of them published in a peer-reviewed journal. This share is considerably higher for exposure and vulnerability data (56%) compared to hazard data (36%). Concerning code availability, one quarter of the exposure and vulnerability data entries provide links to code, and more than half of the hazard data entries make code available.

3.2. STAC browser

The entire catalog inventory is browsable via STAC Browser (Reimann et al., 2026), with step-by-step instructions on how to use it described in a separate user guide (Reimann et al., 2026). The catalog is structured by risk driver and data category that constitute the underlying folder structure (see section 2.1). At the collection level (Fig. 4), STAC Browser provides the collection title and description, followed by the data license, temporal extent, spatial footprint, and provider. It further directly links all items belonging to the same collection. It automatically produces labels for keywords (e.g. exposure, infrastructure footprints), provider roles (e.g. HOST), and the data format of linked items (e.g. GeoTiff).

The item level has a similar layout (Fig. 5), providing item title, spatial footprint, item description, and linking to the overarching collection that the item belongs to. Furthermore, all assets are linked with labels of the asset type and data format, as well as additional resources which include links to publications and available code. All metadata attributes specific to each item (i.e. not included at the collection level) are listed, thereby providing those specifications

Fig. 3. Dataset categories per risk driver currently included in Climate Risk STAC (version 1.0). The respective number of data entries are provided after the category name and are reflected by the relative size of each rectangle.

Critical Infrastructure Spatial Index (CISI)

Description

The Critical Infrastructure Spatial Index (CISI) is calculated from 39 critical infrastructure types (e.g. airports, clinics, landfills, reservoirs, schools) downloaded from Open Street Map (OSM).

(near-)global code available exposure historical
infrastructure footprints modeled

License CC-BY-4.0
Temporal Extent 2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC–2021-12-31 00:00:00 UTC

Provider

Zenodo

HOST

Items 4

Index 0.1 dec deg

GeoTiff CISI at a spatial resolution of 0.1 decimal degrees

2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC–2021-12-31 00:00:00 UTC

Index 0.25 dec deg

GeoTiff CISI at a spatial resolution of 0.25 decimal degrees

2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC–2021-12-31 00:00:00 UTC

Types 0.1 dec deg

GeoTiff CISI infrastructure types at a spatial resolution of 0.1 decimal degrees

2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC–2021-12-31 00:00:00 UTC

Types 0.25 dec deg

GeoTiff CISI infrastructure types at a spatial resolution of 0.25 decimal degrees

2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC–2021-12-31 00:00:00 UTC

Fig. 4. Screenshot of the STAC Browser visualization at the collection level. Example of the collection ‘Critical Infrastructure Spatial Index (CISI)’ in catalog ‘Exposure-vulnerability’ – ‘Infrastructure’ (web browser used: Mozilla Firefox).

relevant for CRAs.

4. Discussion

This first version of the Climate Risk STAC assembles a variety of global-scale datasets across the three climate risk drivers, hazard, exposure, and vulnerability, showcasing the functionality and usability of its technical implementation in STAC. It is the first metadata catalog dedicated specifically to CRA-relevant datasets and includes documentation, including a user guide and contribution instructions (Reimann et al., 2026). In contrast to previous open-access data inventories (see Table 1), Climate Risk STAC has a clearly defined scope that helps users navigate relevant CRA datasets efficiently, supported by an integrated browser for exploring data entries. Being a community-led, living resource, the catalog can grow as its user base increases and new datasets become available. As Climate Risk STAC links rather than hosts data, its storage demands are minimal, enabling long-term maintainability.

While we strive to provide complete and accurate listings of metadata attributes for all catalog entries, we do not take responsibility for their quality, completeness, accuracy, or reliability. Users should assess and verify the suitability of the datasets for their specific applications. Notwithstanding, the open-source and community-driven design allows for improving the overall technical quality and reliability of the datasets included. With an increasing number of users and contributors,

inconsistencies, missing information, or malfunctions will gradually be detected and resolved, resulting in continuous enhancement of the catalog.

Further, we do not claim completeness of the datasets currently included in the catalog and recommend consulting additional data sources before making a final selection of the data to use for the CRA at hand. For instance, while we include all hazard types relevant for CRAs (Fig. 2a), the current data entries may be biased toward flood-related datasets due to the expertise of the data selection team. Similarly, data on snowstorm/blizzard (precipitation-related hazards) and adaptive capacity (population characteristics) are not yet included. To address these gaps, we strongly encourage the CRA community to contribute further datasets, supporting the development of a more complete, FAIR-compliant CRA metadata catalog (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Although we are confident that the technical implementation of the catalog in STAC Browser facilitates data browsing by less technical users, we must note that a certain level of technical expertise is needed for selecting datasets. To support data selection, we define a variety of metadata attributes that do not only include technical specifications of the datasets, but also further useful information such as related publications and code (e.g. for data processing or download), underlying data sources, and relevant notes for using the data. Furthermore, while we facilitate the contribution of additional datasets via a data submission form, a GitHub user account is needed, which may discourage less technical users from adding a dataset. We believe that the catalog

Index 0.1 dec deg

Collection Up Source Share

Asset

<https://zenodo.org/records/4957647/files/CISI.zip?download=1>

DATA
GEOTIFF

Additional Resources

Citation information

- DOI [10.1038/s41597-022-01218-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01218-4)
- [Code link](#)

Description

CISI at a spatial resolution of 0.1 decimal degrees

Collection

Critical Infrastructure Spatial Index (CISI)

The Critical Infrastructure Spatial Index (CISI) is calculated from 39 critical infrastructure types (e.g. airports, clinics, landfills, reservoirs, schools) downloaded...

2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC–2021-12-31 00:00:00 UTC

Metadata

General

Risk Data Type	exposure
Subcategory	infrastructure footprints
Spatial Scale	(near-)global
Reference Period	historical
Temporal Coverage	2021
Scenarios	n/a
Data Type	raster
Data Format	geotiff
Spatial Resolution	0.1 decimal degrees
Source Type	modeled
Analysis Type	equal weighting
Underlying Data	Open Street Map (OSM)
Publication Type	article (see DOI)
Code Type	processing (see Code link)
Usage Notes	The CISI is developed from OSM data and its spatial coverage depends on the completeness of OSM records.
Time of Data begins	2021-01-01 00:00:00 UTC
Time of Data ends	2021-12-31 00:00:00 UTC
Time of Data	n/a

Projection

Code	EPSG:4326
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Scientific

DOI	10.1038/s41597-022-01218-4
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Fig. 5. Screenshot of the STAC Browser visualization at the item level. Example of the item ‘Index 0.1 dec deg’ in collection ‘Critical Infrastructure Spatial Index (CISI)’ (web browser used: Mozilla Firefox).

documentation with guidance on how to navigate STAC Browser and how to contribute new datasets (Reimann et al., 2026) reduces such potential technical barriers.

Climate Risk STAC in its current form includes data entries for hazard, exposure and vulnerability only, but does not integrate datasets that represent the fourth risk determinant ‘response’ as introduced in the latest IPCC Assessment Report (Ara Begum et al., 2022; Simpson et al., 2021). Several efforts have started assembling global evidence on adaptation responses, notably the Global Adaptation Mapping Initiative (GAMI) (Berrang-Ford et al., 2021). However, observed responses are highly fragmented across countries due to financial, institutional, and socioeconomic constraints and are predominantly implemented at local scales (Berrang-Ford et al., 2021; Thomas et al., 2021), which poses a substantial challenge to producing globally consistent geospatial

datasets for this risk determinant. As a result, it is not yet considered in global-scale CRAs. Once such datasets become available, we will extend the catalog accordingly.

While the global-scale CRA data assembled in this first version of Climate Risk STAC produce meaningful results for continental- to global-scale applications, they are less suitable for national or regional CRAs. To support such applications, the catalog is designed to flexibly accommodate datasets at any spatial scale, including global, regional, national, and subnational levels. Moreover, although the current version focuses on geospatial datasets that can be readily used as direct inputs to CRAs, future versions could broaden this scope to include geospatial variables needed to derive those inputs, for example, sea-level rise projections required to model coastal flooding under future conditions.

As the contribution of additional data entries largely depends on the

users' specific applications, we strongly encourage the submission of datasets across all spatial scale and geographical contexts. Since Climate Risk STAC has been developed as part of the EU project CLIMAAX ([The CLIMAAX community, 2025](#)), we anticipate that many new data entries will relate to the European context including continental-scale data, e.g. from the European statistics office ([Eurostat, 2025](#)), and local data from case studies across Europe. However, data submissions are not limited to any particular region, and we envision the catalog evolving into a global resource with data entries from diverse regions around the world. Ultimately, guidance on how to process and analyze the data for the desired CRA is still limited. Once such use cases become available, we envision linking these to the respective data entries of the catalog, thereby facilitating streamlining of CRA concepts, data, and methods. We are planning to include first use cases from CRAs conducted with the help of the CLIMAAX toolbox, for which Climate Risk STAC provides a pool of possible data sources.

Due to its flexible design, Climate Risk STAC provides a strong foundation for a durable, community-oriented resource. Hosted on the well-established collaboration platform GitHub, the catalog is managed through an organizational structure that facilitates shared moderation among multiple administrators. As datasets remain in their original locations, the catalog can accommodate thousands of data entries in a harmonized manner. Looking ahead, we are working on automating the validation procedure of new data submissions to minimize the need for manual moderation and consequently reduce dependence on dedicated resources. In the meantime, we also welcome community support in moderating data submissions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lena Reimann: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dirk Eilander:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Conceptualization. **Timothy Tiggeloven:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Conceptualization. **Milana Vuckovic:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Matti Kumm:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Andrea Vajda:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jeremy S. Pal:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Maurizio Mazzoleni:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Fredrik Wetterhall:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Jeroen C.J.H. Aerts:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Software and data availability

- Name of software: climate-risk-stac (version 1.0)
- Developers: climate-risk-data organization
- Contact: through the issues function on GitHub
- Date first available: February 13, 2026 (version 1.0)
- Software required: Python (version ≥ 3.12), STAC (version $\geq 1.0.0$), PySTAC (version ≥ 1.10), STAC Browser (version $\geq 3.3.5$)
- Program language: Python
- Source code at: <https://github.com/climate-risk-data/climate-risk-stac> (Reimann et al., 2026) and on Zenodo (Reimann et al., 2026)
- Documentation: Detailed documentation of the purpose of Climate Risk Stac, a user guide, and instruction on how to contribute can be found at <https://climate-risk-data.github.io/climate-risk-stac/> (Reimann et al., 2026)
- No data are required for using the software.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2026.106906>.

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